

TMT Adaptive Optics Facility Status Report

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ABSTRACT

The TMT first-light adaptive optics (AO) facility comprises the Narrow Field InfraRed AO System (NFIRAOS), the Laser Guide Star Facility (LGSF), and the AO Executive Software (AOESW). NFIRAOS is a 60x60-order laser guide star (LGS) multi-conjugate AO (MCAO) system providing uniform, diffraction-limited performance in J, H, and K bands over a 34 arcsecond diameter field with 50% sky coverage at the Galactic pole. Since the last reporting period, substantial progress has been made across all subsystems. The NFIRAOS deformable mirror actuator lines are fully fabricated and tested at CILAS, and the deformable mirror electronics final design has been completed at NRC. The real-time controller (RTC) has surpassed 60 software releases and has been validated on-sky at 1 kHz with the NRC REVOLT bench. The LGSF completed its first Final Design Review (FDR-1) in January 2026. The first-light NFIRAOS-fed science instruments IRIS and MODHIS have passed their respective FDR-1 and Conceptual Design Reviews, while WFOS completed its PDR-1. This paper summarizes the current status and highlights key developments across AO systems, wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, laser systems, instruments, and AO system engineering.

Keywords: adaptive optics, extremely large telescope, MCAO, deformable mirror, laser guide star, real-time controller, NFIRAOS, IRIS, MODHIS, TMT

1. INTRODUCTION

The Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) is a next-generation extremely large telescope (ELT) currently in advanced design across all its major systems. TMT completes the global network of ELTs alongside the ESO ELT and GMT, offering full northern-sky access for the world's astronomical community. More than 85% of the TMT project is now in final design or beyond, including the AO facility that will underpin its first-light science program.

The first-light AO architecture has remained stable for many years: an LGS MCAO system (NFIRAOS) corrects atmospheric wavefront errors and feeds two science instruments, the Infrared Imaging Spectrograph (IRIS) and the Multi-Objective Diffraction-limited High-resolution Infrared Spectrograph (MODHIS). A Laser Guide Star Facility (LGSF) generates up to eight sodium laser guide stars in four selectable asterism configurations. The AO Executive Software (AOESW) coordinates all AO subsystems with the broader observatory for safe and efficient observations. The seeing-limited Wide Field Optical Spectrometer (WFOS) rounds out the first-light instrument suite. When TMT adopts an adaptive secondary mirror, WFOS is compatible with a Ground Layer AO system upgrade.

This paper provides an incremental update to the status report presented at AO4ELT7 [1], reflecting developments through early 2026. Section 2 summarizes the first-light architecture and maturity. Sections 3 through 5 cover NFIRAOS, the LGSF, and AOESW respectively. Section 6 addresses AO system engineering and simulations, including petalling and sky-coverage studies. Section 7 describes instrument status, and Section 8 presents a brief summary.

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Figure 1. TMT first-light instrumentation architecture. NFIRAOS is mounted on the -X Nasmyth platform and feeds IRIS (bottom port) and MODHIS (top port). The LGSF laser heads are attached to the elevation journal and are launched from a telescope behind M2. WFOS occupies the +X Nasmyth platform.

2. TMT FIRST-LIGHT INSTRUMENTATION ARCHITECTURE

The TMT optical design is a 30 m diameter Ritchey-Chretien with a segmented 492-segment primary mirror (M1), a 3.1 m convex secondary (M2), and a flat articulated tertiary (M3, 2.5 m x 3.6 m) with a 20 arcminute field of view that enables rapid instrument switching between the two Nasmyth platforms. Table 1 summarizes the maturity of the AO systems and first-light instruments as of early 2026, demonstrating the substantial progress made since AO4ELT7.

3. NARROW FIELD INFRARED AO SYSTEM (NFIRAOS)

NFIRAOS completed its external Final Design Review in 2018 and is now progressing to production readiness. The system corrects atmospheric and telescope wavefront errors at up to 800 Hz and operates at -30° C to meet stringent background-emission requirements. It includes two high-order deformable mirrors (DMs) conjugated at 0 km (DM0, 63x63 actuators) and 11.8 km (DM11, 76x76 actuators), six 60x60 LGS Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors, a pyramid natural guide star (NGS) WFS, and a tip-tilt stage. Expected Strehl ratios are $\sim 71\%$ in K band for LGS MCAO and $\sim 84\%$ in K band for bright star NGS AO at median seeing conditions.

Table 1. TMT AO and instrumentation maturity as of early 2026. FDR = Final Design Review; PDR = Preliminary Design Review; CoDR = Conceptual Design Review.

System / Subsystem	Component	Current Phase	Technical Maturity / Recent Milestones
NFIRAOS	System	Production Readiness	FDR completed 2018
	Real-Time Controller (RTC)	Fabrication	~60 software releases delivered; HEART RTC tested on-sky at 1 kHz with REVOLT bench (NRC)
	DMs (DM0 / DM11)	Fabrication	DM0: all 243 actuator lines fabricated and tested at CILAS; DM0 assembly starting 2026
	DM Electronics (DME)	Production Readiness	Final design completed at NRC; modular design, 2x96 channels per module. Prototyping in progress.
	LGS WFS (Sony IMX425)	Commercial Fab Readiness	Re-baselined to C-BLUE One camera; closed-loop on-sky at 1 kHz on DAO 1.2m + REVOLT bench
	NGS Pyramid WFS (EMCCD220)	Commercial Fab Readiness	Re-baselined to Teledyne E2V EMCCD220; minimal NFIRAOS design changes required
LGSF	System	Final Design	FDR-1 completed January 2026; CFD modeling verifies WFE budget; athermal powered optics design
	Sodium Lasers	Commercial Fab Readiness	Toptica/MPBC baseline; units mounted on telescope elevation journal
AOESW	AO Sequencer	Final Design	PDR completed November 2025; non-sidereal tracking sequences under development
IRIS	First Light AO Instrument	Final Design	FDR-1 completed December 2025; H4RG-15 imager update; LN2 autofill complete; Keck LIGER hardware sharing
MODHIS	First Light AO Instrument	Preliminary Design	CoDR passed September 2025; spectropolarimetric mode added; shares design with Keck HISPEC (in fabrication)
WFOS	Seeing-limited Instrument	Preliminary Design	PDR-1 passed August 2025; CSU replaces slit masks; IFU added to baseline design

3.1 Deformable Mirrors

Both NFIRAOS deformable mirrors are being manufactured under contract by CILAS (France) using piezoelectric (PZT) actuator technology, following successful prototype testing of a 28x28 DM that met or exceeded all TMT requirements. The most significant recent milestone is the completion of the DM0 actuator lines: each line contains a row of PZT actuators, and all have been fully fabricated and electrically tested at CILAS, representing 100% completion of this critical manufacturing step. Assembly of DM0 is scheduled to begin in early 2026. DM11 lines fabrication is continuing on schedule. Both DMs must achieve 10 micron peak-to-valley stroke after flattening at -30° C with very low hysteresis, nonlinearity, and creep.

Figure 2. Left: DM0 actuator lines at CILAS. All 243 lines have been completed and tested, representing 100% completion of this manufacturing milestone. Right: CAD rendering of one DME module controlling 2x96 channels; DM0 will use 17 such modules and DM11 will require 24.

3.2 Deformable Mirror Electronics and Wavefront Sensor Cameras

The Deformable Mirror Electronics (DME) final design has been successfully completed at NRC-Herzberg. The modular DME architecture groups 2x96 actuator channels per module; DM0 requires 17 modules and DM11 requires 24. This modular approach facilitates testing and in-field replacement.

The NFIRAOS LGS wavefront sensors have been re-baselined to commercial Sony IMX425 CMOS detectors via the First Light Imaging C-BLUE One camera, replacing the original custom polar-coordinate CCD development. Each LGS WFS operates with a 75x75 Shack-Hartmann subaperture grid and 11x11 pixels per subaperture, yielding a 1 arcsecond pixel scale. The C-BLUE One camera has been extensively validated: the NRC team successfully closed the AO loop at 1 kHz on both the REVOLT laboratory bench and the DAO 1.2 m telescope on-sky. The NGS pyramid WFS has been re-baselined to a commercial Teledyne E2V EMCCD220 detector, offering superior sensitivity and reduced development risk compared to the original custom solution.

3.3 Real-Time Controller and AO Software

The NFIRAOS Real-Time Controller (RTC) is in active production, with approximately 60 software releases delivered to TMT to date [2]. The RTC architecture uses commercial CPU server hardware with a classical Matrix-Vector-Multiply (MVM) wavefront reconstruction algorithm, solving the tomographic control problem (55k x 8k matrix at 800 Hz) across six High-Order Processing (HOP) servers, one per LGS WFS channel. The NRC HEART RTC, the development platform for the NFIRAOS RTC, has been validated in closed-loop operation at 1 kHz on-sky at the DAO 1.2 m telescope using the NRC REVOLT bench [3].

The AOESW comprises three coordinated subsystems: the AO Sequencer (AOSQ), the Reconstructor Parameter Generator (RPG), and the Point Spread Function Reconstructor (PSFR). Under direction from the Observatory Control System, the AOSQ orchestrates all AO hardware including NFIRAOS, the LGSF, and the on-instrument wavefront sensors, while the RPG updates the tomographic control matrix for the RTC before and during each observation, and the PSFR reconstructs science-quality PSFs from RTC telemetry in post-processing. The AO Sequencer component of the AOESW completed its Preliminary Design Review in November 2025.

4. LASER GUIDE STAR FACILITY (LGSF)

The LGSF BTO Optical Path completed its Final Design Review-1 in January 2026, a major milestone for this complex subsystem. A second review (FDR-2) covering the remaining LGSF subsystems, is planned to complete the Final Design phase. The LGSF generates four selectable asterisms (MCAO, LTAO, MOAO, and GLAO) with up to eight sodium LGS, using commercial Toptica/MPBC sodium laser units mounted on the TMT elevation journal. At first light, six laser units will be installed to support the MCAO/NFIRAOS asterism; two additional units are required only for the MOAO asterism. The beam transfer optics route up to eight laser beams in a 3x3 pattern (no central beam) along the elevation structure to the top end, where an asterism generator and common powered optics (collimator and laser launch telescope) format and launch the beams from a central launch aperture.

Three stages of magnification are implemented as fully athermal refractive beam expanders. CFD thermal modeling [4] was used to assess and optimize the thermal performance of the powered optics, and focus mechanisms are incorporated

as needed to compensate for laser-induced transient heating. The CFD analysis confirms that thermally induced focus errors are within the compensation range of the focus mechanisms and validates the wavefront error budget allocation. Global flexure compensation is performed by three large, actuated fold-mirrors in gimbal mounts, the Truss Pointing Mirror and two Hexapod Fold Mirrors, each driven in tip/tilt by two actuators based on feedback from Pre-Alignment Cameras distributed along the optical path. A separate array of fast-steering mirrors in the Asterism Generator provides per-beam uplink turbulence correction. A diagnostic system at the top end is always available, even during observations. The LGSF optical design achieves an LGS e-2 intensity diameter of no larger than 0.8 arcseconds at the sodium layer.

Figure 4. LGSF final design. Left: overview of the beam path from laser heads on the elevation journal to the center-launch projection system at the top end. Right: detail of the Laser Launch Telescope.

5. AO SYSTEM ENGINEERING AND SIMULATIONS

5.1 Performance Budget and Key Performance Parameters

Extensive work has continued on AO requirement traceability from high-level science cases down to subsystem and component requirements. AO Key Performance Parameters (KPPs) have been formally defined and are tracked by system engineering. These include: LGS MCAO and NGS AO wavefront error, acquisition time, astrometric and photometric accuracy, pupil stability, and vibration budgets. Table 2 summarizes the current best-estimate (CBE) wavefront error and corresponding K-band Strehl ratios for the primary NFIRAOS observing modes under median observing conditions, demonstrating positive margin on all requirements.

Table 2. NFIRAOS AO performance. Conditions: median seeing ($r_0 = 18.6$ cm), medium wind-speed profile, median sky coverage at Galactic Pole, 30 degrees zenith angle.

Observing Mode	WFE Req [nm]	WFE CBE [nm]	K-band Strehl
NGS AO (R = 8 guide star)	158	146	84%
NGS AO (R = 12 guide star)	167	156	82%
LGS MCAO on-axis	215	205	71%
LGS MCAO averaged (34"x34" field)	233	225	66%

5.2 Petalling Mode Sensing and Correction

A potential concern for ELT AO systems is the excitation of petalling modes. These are low-order wavefront errors, predominantly piston, separated across the M2 spider arms, and can degrade AO performance if not corrected. Sources include low-wind effect dome seeing, phasing or stacking errors under spider vignetting, and noise propagation or aliasing in the RTC. For TMT, simulations demonstrate that petalling is not a major performance driver [5], primarily because the TMT M2 spiders are very thin (225 mm). The thin spider geometry minimizes the low-wind effect (contributing only ~30 nm of wavefront error impact) and has negligible effect on the phasing accuracy due to the significant redundancy of the phasing measurements.

As a risk-reduction measure, a Hybrid Iterative Petalling Sensor (HIPS) has been developed and demonstrated in simulation. HIPS detects and corrects petalling modes by exploiting tip/tilt/focus and tip-tilt WFS PSF information, requiring no additional hardware beyond the existing NFIRAOS wavefront sensing infrastructure.

5.3 Alignment and Phasing System

The TMT Alignment and Phasing System (APS) measures and adjusts piston, tip, tilt, and segment figure for all 492 primary mirror segments, and aligns M2 and M3. The APS is based on the Keck Phasing Camera System (PCS), which has accumulated more than 60 years of combined operational heritage on the two Keck telescopes. Critically, all TMT phasing requirements have already been demonstrated on-sky at Keck, providing strong confidence in the approach. The PEAS (Procedure Executor and Analysis Software) operational at Keck since 2016 will serve as the APS control environment, providing a web-based GUI with full-mirror visualization, database archiving, and continuous algorithm development. Recent improvements at Keck, including warping harness algorithms, terrace-mode calibration, phase-dispersion correction, and a Zernike WFS mode requiring minimal additional hardware, directly benefit TMT through the continuous Keck-TMT innovation loop.

6. FIRST-LIGHT INSTRUMENTS

6.1 IRIS: Infrared Imaging Spectrograph

IRIS is TMT's workhorse near-infrared imager and integral field spectrograph, mounted on the bottom port of NFIRAOS [6]. Its science channel provides a 34x34 arcsecond imager field (4 mas pixels) and an IFS with selectable spaxel scales from 4 to 50 mas/spaxel, spanning 0.84-2.4 microns. IRIS completed its System FDR-1 in December 2025. Key design updates include adoption of H4RG-15 HgCdTe detectors for the imager, completion of the liquid-nitrogen autofill system design for cryogenic operations, and fabrication of duplicate IFS TMA (Three-Mirror Anastigmat) and grating turret assemblies for the Keck LIGER instrument, an approach that simultaneously advances TMT and validates IRIS designs on a near-term facility instrument. The three IRIS On-Instrument Wavefront Sensors (OIWFS) use C-RED One APD cameras for near-IR tip/tilt/focus sensing with high sky coverage.

6.2 MODHIS: Multi-Objective Diffraction-limited High-resolution Infrared Spectrograph

MODHIS provides fiber-fed, diffraction-limited, high-resolution ($R \geq 100,000$) near-infrared spectroscopy over 0.95-2.4 microns, targeting exoplanet science including transit spectroscopy, direct spectroscopy, and precision radial velocity measurements with a goal of 50 cm/s PRV precision [7]. MODHIS passed its Conceptual Design Review in September 2025. Following reviewer recommendations, a spectro-polarimetric mode has been added to the baseline design. MODHIS shares its spectrograph design with the Keck HISPEC instrument, which is currently in fabrication, providing strong near-term heritage. The top-end module (support structure, rotator, OIWFS, and front-end instrument) is mounted on NFIRAOS, with the spectrographs located off-telescope and connected via single-mode fibers.

6.3 WFOS: Wide Field Optical Spectrometer

WFOS is TMT's seeing-limited optical multi-object spectrograph, offering an 8x3 arcminute field of view with spectral resolutions from $R \sim 1,500$ to 7,500 and full wavelength coverage from 310 to 1000 nm at $R \sim 1,500$ [8]. WFOS passed its PDR-1 in August 2025. Notable design changes include replacement of traditional slit masks with a Configurable Slit Unit (CSU) enabling rapid reconfiguration, and the addition of an Integral Field Unit (IFU) to the baseline design. WFOS is designed to be upgradeable to Ground Layer Adaptive Optics (GLAO) when TMT commissions its adaptive secondary mirror.

7. SUMMARY

The TMT first-light AO facility has made substantial progress since AO4ELT7. NFIRAOS remains on track for production readiness: all DM0 actuator lines have been fabricated and tested at CILAS, the deformable mirror electronics final design is complete at NRC, and the RTC has surpassed 60 software releases with on-sky validation at 1 kHz. Both the LGS and NGS WFS cameras have been successfully re-baselined to lower-risk commercial detectors. The LGSF Beam Transfer Optics completed its FDR-1 in January 2026, with CFD modeling confirming the wavefront error budget. The AO Sequencer completed its PDR in November 2025. IRIS completed its FDR-1 in December 2025, MODHIS its CoDR in September 2025, and WFOS its PDR-1 in August 2025. AO system engineering continues to demonstrate positive margin on all performance requirements, with petalling shown to be non-critical for TMT and all phasing requirements already validated on-sky at Keck. TMT remains firmly committed to finding a path to construction, with the project now more than 85% in final design or beyond.

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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